

THE ART OF EMBROIDERY AND ITS SOME ASPECTS

Shomirzaev Makhmatmurad Khuramovich

Professor of Termiz State University,
Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc)

The city of Termiz, Surkhandarya region, Republic of Uzbekistan

Email: terdu.shomirzayev@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7947243>

Summary. The article highlights aspects of embroidery. It is argued that embroidery is an interesting and creative work that can bring the world a lot of joy, fun and excitement.

Key words and concepts: embroidery, profession, profession, interest, education, upbringing, passion, skills, qualification.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoev emphasized the importance of "paying special attention to the family, which is the most important, I would say decisive, aspect of our society in raising a healthy and well-rounded generation..." In fact, since ancient times, the family has served as a school for young people to learn their profession, to form their spiritual and moral qualities, and to prepare them for life. In this regard, our forefathers paid special attention to the interest in labor and profession in the education of children. So, in the 21st century, it is important for every parent to pay attention to the profession of their children in the family. Because a child's attitude to work begins first of all with the family.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev said, "Today, all our work is done for the happiness of our children and their bright future. But happiness is not determined only by wealth and possessions. A polite, knowledgeable and intelligent, hardworking, faith-believing child is the greatest wealth not only of parents, but of the whole society"¹.

Therefore, whether each child becomes a builder, a tailor, or a craftsman in the future, it depends on the upbringing of the family and his hard work. In this regard, the Uzbek family has long paid great attention to the psychological and pedagogical aspects of child rearing, how it will grow up in the future, the requirements for ensuring continuity of generations, the continuity and integrity of upbringing.

Of course, family education was considered important in teaching children a profession. In this regard, over the centuries, children's education, its moral aspects, the child's becoming a qualified professional, living honestly and cleanly in life, and working hard have been raised to the level of high values.

In ancient times, parents respected the teacher who taught their children a trade. The culture of relationship between parents and teachers has its own characteristics. Qualities such as showing affection and kindness of the parents to the teacher, correctly understanding the teacher's rebuke to their child, providing the necessary things for their child to learn a trade, and pleasing the teacher are considered important factors in child education. Also, the teacher had a specific attitude towards parents. They have their own characteristics of nationality, educational opportunities, teacher-student traditions, morals between them, such as fulfilling the responsible task they have undertaken to teach their students, to go beyond

their promises, to speak openly to parents about their child's abilities and behavior. The criterion of etiquette and culture was considered important in educating the young generation in the spirit of love for the profession of national folk crafts.

It should be noted that the basis of child education in an Uzbek household begins with the family. The profession of the parents in the society, their reputation in the neighborhood, as an important factor of upbringing, has a great impact on the outlook, knowledge and behavior of children. So, family is one of the factors of teachers' interest in the profession.

In most cases, the child's interest in the profession is formed on the basis of imitating his parents, brothers, relatives, that is, his elders. Forming and educating a perfect person in society is an important task of the modern family. Because a person's interest in any trade or profession first of all arises in the family. A certain political-ideological outlook, moral standards, behavior patterns, and physical qualities are inculcated in a person through family upbringing. As a result of this process, which takes place in the family, the person ultimately assimilates social norms and values and enters social life.

Embroidery plays an important role in decorating clothes and items. Knowing how to embroider, you can update clothes, decorate and prepare many necessary items: napkins, aprons, aprons, pillowcases, gifts for loved ones.

Embroidery is an interesting and creative work that can bring a lot of joy to a person, can be a pastime in his free time, and can introduce a person to the world of sophistication. When learning embroidery techniques, everything may not go well at once, because embroidery requires patience, attention, order. Therefore, the embroiderer should be patient. As you acquire the necessary practical skills and competencies, the work will gradually become easier.

There is a centuries-old history of the art of embroidery, according to archeological findings, since ancient times household items - towels, lace border, tablecloths, holiday and everyday clothes, shawls, embroidery methods, flowers, and the embodiment of colors have been improved from generation to generation. Gradually, good embroideries were selected, and unique embroidery samples were created, characterized by national characteristics, and hats and other items were decorated with embroideries.

Items decorated with embroidery by folk masters are distinguished by beautiful flowers, harmony of colors, full proportions, and professional accuracy of execution methods. Each embroidered item has a practical function.

Many examples of folk embroidery are collected in the museums of our country, especially the embroidery of the 19th century has been well preserved and has survived to this day. Uzbek national embroidery (embroidery) is one of the ancient types of practical art, which arose as a result of the people's desire to make their life beautiful. The art of embroidery has gained fame not only in our country, but also in foreign countries. Uzbek folk craftsmen sewed kirpech, sozana, zardevor, flower quilt, bedclothes etc. Federal Republic of Germany, Belgium, United States of America. Recognized in foreign universities such as India and Afghanistan. Also, in the Fergana Valley of our country, it has become a permanent exhibition not only in homes, but also in museums. Until now, the products have been surprising people with their unique beauty and the colorfulness of the elegant decorations. Artistic embroidery has a long history, as evidenced by archaeological finds and written sources. Uzbek embroidery has developed together with all professions in connection with

the climate, natural conditions, environment. The most ancient art of embroidery has not been preserved.

Through the miniatures of the 14th and 15th centuries, it can be seen that embroidery has been developed for a very long time. Spanish ambassador Rui Gonzalez de Clavijo recorded in his diary that he saw Uzbek national embroidery decorations in Amir Temur's palace. In 1467, Kamoliddin Behzod worked for "Zafarnoma" in the miniature "Temur Takhtda" depicting a chestnut tree used for a tent¹. In the second half of the 19th century, the invention of the embroidery machine laid the foundation for the creation of embroidery enterprises. The large production of embroidery by machines has damaged their artistry, and as a result, flower embroidery has been forgotten. But only some types have been preserved. Uzbek embroidery was enriched and developed under the influence of embroidery of neighboring nations. If we look at Uzbek embroiderers, we can find the methods and styles of Indian, Chinese, Russian, Afghan, Kazakh, Kyrgyz and Tajik embroiderers.

Uzbek embroiderers have a lot of plant-like, geometric and floral motifs, while Russian embroidery often depicts geometric, plant-like shapes, flowers, birds and fruits. In Kazakh and Kyrgyz embroidery, elements reminiscent of animals, horns and hooves are depicted. According to ancient traditions, Uzbek girls - brides-to-be's dowries had to prepare all kinds of embroidery items themselves. The finer and more beautiful the embroideries were, the higher the value. Girls were taught to embroider from the age of 7-9. They begin to embroider independently after three or four years. Mature embroiderers tried to express their dreams of beauty according to their art and nature. Teaching folk art, its types and the history of embroidery art is one of the important factors in children's education. Because in the centuries-old history of the Uzbek people, folk decorative art is the main part of our cultural heritage.

The types of applied arts that have flourished in the Uzbek land are world famous for their originality and uniqueness. This is a stage of development when we think about it, we witness that the origin of Uzbek applied decorative art goes back to the first era of mankind, that is, to the era of the primitive community. In the recent past, the most developed types of Uzbek applied decorative arts, such as embroidery, needlework, stone and bone carving, needlework, knife making, felt making, jewelry, goldsmithing, carpet making, felting, basketry, etc. schools, styles, and the services of masters who became famous in these fields are known all over the world.

The art of Central Asian embroidery has been known to the world since ancient times. The beauty that our forefathers used in the past has not lost its charm to this day. The exquisite embroideries still amaze us. Embroidery is an Arabic word that means image, flower, and it is an ornament created by the repetition of birds, animals, flora, geometric and various other forms in a certain order. Artistic embroidery is the art of creating beauty in color combinations and original compositions. In his work, the craftsman skillfully uses the natural gloss and harmony of colors, the graceful shape, the texture of the material, and achieves vivid expression.

Since ancient times, our ancestors used to decorate fabrics with elegant images, describing their dreams, love and wishes through them. Our artisan forefathers deeply and comprehensively studied the human psyche and enriched them with wonderful embroidery designs. Wise grandfathers have proven for centuries based on their life experiences that

people will be calm and peaceful in a house decorated with embroidery, and that a person will live a long life in such an environment.

No matter what type of folk art it is, it is based on a composition of embroidery elements. The decorative elements of the embroidery composition are created by simplifying the description of flowers, branches, leaves, birds and animals found in nature.

The embroidery compositions of each oases and cities are unique. For example, Tashkent, Khorezm, Fergana, Samarkand, Bukhara, Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya embroidery schools have their own shapes and colors. In the process of creating an independent composition, embroidery elements are interconnected by stylization. Emphasis is placed on the functions and smooth drawing of the embroidery pieces. A composition is made from elements of flower, leaf, branch, fabric and double thread embroidery.

"The natural skills, abilities and characteristics that a person needs for a lifetime, for example, each child's unique and suitable abilities, communication with the people around him, how he feels among his peers, whether he has leadership qualities or not, if necessary, his worldview - these are life experience confirms in many examples that everything, first of all, is inextricably linked to his innate nature, at the same time, to the upbringing he receives in the family."

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Based on Mirziyoev's ideas, to create programs in order to form interest in folk decorative art in children from a young age, it is desirable to conduct trainings, prepare handouts and didactic materials on drawing embroidered pictures. Therefore, it is important for children in the family to have an understanding of the art of embroidery and to form initial skills and competencies during training.

In the future, the wide application of information technologies in the educational process is aimed at enriching the content of education, improving it and accelerating the acquisition of students' knowledge, solving the problems of cooperation and individual education and complex design. This requires the creation of a new generation of textbooks and training manuals that cover all educational technologies and are focused on practical application.

The regular participation of students in different exhibitions, competitions and their creative works on different topics shows that they have high skills and qualifications. In order for them to participate in various exhibitions and competitions, they receive spiritual nourishment and to deepen their knowledge, it is of particular importance to teach the secrets of national crafts to schoolchildren in this field, to inform them about the elements of patterns and types of decorative items in embroidery.

It is known that any pattern is used to decorate things, that is, dishes, clothes, gazmol, building, avenue and so on. When drawing a pattern, mainly two forms are used, i.e. natural and geometric forms. Plants, animals and birds are the subject of pattern art. Leaf, tulip, pepper, rose, cotton, pomegranate, pear, egg, grape, peacock, pigeon, mouse, butterfly, fox, turtle, bird, lion, goose, fish, beetle, samovar, kettle, telephone, star, kettle and the appearance of other items can be based on the pattern.

References:

1. Shomirzayev, M. K., & Yuldashov, K. K. (2021). The Educational Importance of Teaching Knowledge to Secondary School Students. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 2(08), 132-142.
2. Shomirzayev, M. K. (2020). Education is personally focused technology. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 8(8).
3. Shomirzayev, M. K. (2020). National handicrafts of Uzbekistan and its social-economic significance. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(8), 129-138.
4. Shomirzayev, M. K., & Yuldashov, K. K. (2021). The Educational Importance of Teaching Knowledge to Secondary School Students. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 2(08), 132-142.
5. Shomirzayev, M. K., & Pakhratdinova, R. O. (2021). Characteristics of Organization and Conduct of Practical Courses on National Crafts in Technology. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 11(9), 182-192.
6. Shomirzayev, M. K. (2020). The concept of pedagogical technology and basic principles. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 1551-1560.
7. Shomirzayev, M. K. The Concept of Pedagogical Technology and Basic Principles. *Academicia: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. (Affiliated to Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra, India), Vol. 10, Issue 11, November 2020 Scientific Journal Impact Factor (Sjif 2020-7.13). Part 1554-1563.
8. Shomirzayev, M. K. (2019). The Ethical Characteristics of Traditional Embroidery of Fergana Valley People. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 7(12).
9. Shomirzayev, M. K. (2020). Technology of Educational Process in School Technology Education. *The American Journal of Social Science and Educational Innovations*, 2(07), 212-223.
10. Shomirzayev, M. K. (2020). Ethnic characteristics of national traditional crafts. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 8(12), 216-225.